

Glutathione depletion is involved in the inhibition of procollagen $\alpha 1(I)$ mRNA levels caused by TNF- α on hepatic stellate cells

Authors

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Abstract

TNF- α has been shown to inhibit procollagen $\alpha 1(I)$ expression in hepatic stellate cells (HSC), although the molecular mechanisms involved have not been fully established. In the present work, we studied the possible role played by oxidative stress and NF κ B on the antifibrogenic action of TNF- α on a cell line of rat HSC. Treatment of HSC with TNF- α did not affect either intracellular levels of reactive oxygen species or lipid peroxidation, but caused a decrease on reduced glutathione (GSH) levels. Restoration of intracellular GSH by incubation with exogenous GSH prevented the inhibition of procollagen $\alpha 1(I)$ levels caused by TNF- α . The effect of GSH was not mimicked by antioxidants like deferoxamine, tempol or trolox. Activation of NF κ B by TNF- α was also abolished by preincubation of HSC with GSH, but not by deferoxamine, tempol or trolox. These results point to GSH depletion as a mediator of TNF- α action in HSC.

Keywords

TNF- α ; Type I collagen; Hepatic stellate cells; Glutathione; NF κ B.

1. Introduction

Oxidative stress has been shown to induce the expression of extracellular matrix proteins in different cell types, including mesangial cells [1], skin fibroblasts [2], periacinar pancreatic cells [3], and hepatic stellate cells (HSC) [4]. The role played by oxidative stress in collagen production by HSC is especially well established. In several liver pathologies in which oxidative stress is induced, HSC present an activated phenotype characterized by production of the fibrogenic cytokine TGF- β and induction of proteins of the extracellular matrix, mainly collagen type I [5]. *In vivo* and *in vitro* studies have also shown a relationship between oxidative stress and collagen production in HSC through different molecular mechanisms, such as direct induction of procollagen $\alpha 1(I)$ (coll1a1) gene expression by intracellular hydrogen peroxide generated in response to TGF- β [6], acetaldehyde [7], or by membrane lipid peroxidation [8]. Together with TGF- β , other cytokines produced by macrophages or Kupffer cells during the pathogenic process, like tumor necrosis alpha (TNF- α), could contribute to the regulation of collagen production in the liver. However, there are some paradoxical data about the effects of TNF- α on oxidative stress and collagen production. On the one hand, TNF- α has been described as an oxidative stress inductor in several cell types, since it provokes lipid peroxidation and increased production of reactive oxygen species (ROS), and some of its effects are blocked by antioxidants [9–12]; on the other, TNF- α is an antifibrogenic cytokine, inhibiting type I collagen synthesis by down-regulation of coll1a1 and coll1a2 gene expression

[13,14] . Several effects of TNF- α are mediated by NF κ B, a nuclear factor that has been shown to be induced by oxidative stress in some systems and that presents antiproliferative and antifibrogenic effects on HSC [15,16]. The aim of the present work is to analyze the possible role played by oxidative stress on procollagen α 1(I) down-regulation caused by TNF- α in HSC and its relationship with NF κ B activation.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Reagents

TNF- α , glutathione, deferoxamine, tempol and trolox were purchased from Sigma (St. Louis, Missouri, US). Cellculture reagents were from Gibco BRL. 5-6-chloromethyl 2', 7'-dichlorohydrofluorescein diacetate (CM-H₂DCFDA) was from Molecular Probes (Eugene, OR). NF κ B consensus sequence was obtained from Santa Cruz Biotechnology (Santa Cruz, CA).

2.2 Cell culture and materials

All the experiments were performed using the HSC line CFSC-2G that has a similar phenotype to that of partially activated HSC [17]. Cells were cultured in MEM supplemented with 10% bovine fetal serum and non-essential amino acids for 36 h after which the medium was replaced for a serum-free medium. Treatments were carried out 12 h later. Unless otherwise indicated, HSC were treated with 20 ng/ml TNF- α for 24 h. In some experiments cells were pretreated for 30 min with either 1.0- or 2.0-mM glutathione, 0.1 mM deferoxamine, 2 mM tempol or 1 mM trolox.

2.3 Measurement of ROS production

Reactive oxygen species (ROS) levels were measured using the fluorescent probe CM-H₂DCFDA. For these experiments HSC were grown in MEM without phenol red. HSC were plated to subconfluence in 12 well plates, treated for different times with 20 ng/ml TNF- α , and then incubated for 20 min with 5 μ M CM-H₂DCFDA at room temperature. Fluorescence was analyzed in a Cytofluor 2350 (excitation at 485 nm, emission at 530 nm).

2.4 Measurement of intracellular GSH levels

Intracellular levels of glutathione (reduced form, GSH) were determined by the method of Hissin and Hilf [18]. HSC were cultured and treated as described above. After treatment, HSC were scraped and resuspended in MEM (1×10^6 cell/ml). An aliquot of the deproteinized cell suspension (50 μ l) was mixed with 2.1 ml of 200 mM sodium phosphate buffer, pH 8.0, containing 5 mM EDTA. Then 100 μ l of a solution of o-phthaldialdehyde (1 mg/ml in methanol) was added, and 15 min later the intensity of fluorescence was determined (excitation 350 nm, emission 420 nm).

2.5 Measurement of lipid peroxidation

Lipid peroxidation was determined by assay for thiobarbituric acid reactive substances (TBARS) at 535 nm, asdescribed by Buege and Aust [19]. HSC were scraped and resuspended in PBS (1×10^6 cell/ml) and aliquots (500 μ l) were precipitated with 1.0 ml of 10% trichloroacetic

acid (TCA) and centrifuged for 20 s at 6000 rpm. Aliquots (1.0 ml) of the supernatants were added to an equal volume of 1% thiobarbituric acid and the mixture was heated for 10 min in a boiling water bath and allowed to cool down. The absorbance at 535 nm was determined. TBARS are represented as malondialdehyde equivalents, calculated using an extinction coefficient of $1.6 \times 10^5 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

2.6 RNA extraction and Northern blot analysis

Total RNA was extracted as described by Chomczynski and Sacchi [20]. Northern blot assays were performed using 10 μg of total RNA per lane and hybridization with ^{32}P -labeled probes for procollagen $\alpha 1(\text{I})$ (coll1a1) and 18s ribosomal RNA. Autoradiographic signals were quantitated by scanning densitometry.

2.7 Nuclear protein extraction and electrophoretic mobility shift assays (EMSA).

HSC cultured as described above, were treated for 2 h with 20 ng/ml of TNF- α . Nuclear proteins from control and experimental cell cultures were isolated following the method described by Schreiber et al. [21]. The consensus sequence for NF κ B was labeled with [γ ^{32}P]ATP using T4 polynucleotide kinase. The reaction mixture (25 μl final volume) containing 40% glycerol, 1 μg of dIdC, 10 mM EDTA, 20 mM DTT, 100 mM Tris-HCl buffer pH 7.5, 10,000 cpm of labeled oligonucleotide and 10 μg of nuclear extract, were incubated for 30 min at 4°C. DNA-protein complexes were separated from unbound probe by electrophoresis on a 5% polyacrylamide gel. Complexes formed were identified by autoradiography of the dried gels. For supershift assays, incubation mixtures contained 1 μg of the corresponding specific antibody.

2.8 Statistical analysis.

Data were analyzed using the Kruskal-Wallis test to determine differences between all independent groups. When significant differences were obtained ($p < 0.05$), differences between two groups were tested using the Mann-Whitney U test.

3. Results

3.1 Oxidative-stress parameters in TNF- α -treated HSC

We first analyzed the effect of TNF- α on three parameters related to the generation of oxidative stress: accumulation of reactive oxygen species (ROS), the extent of membrane lipid peroxidation and intracellular levels of reduced glutathione (GSH). ROS accumulation was measured using the fluorescent probe 5-6-chloromethyl-2',7'-dichloro hydrofluorescein diacetate (CM-H₂DCFDA), using menadione as a positive control. TNF- α did not produce any detectable change on the accumulation of ROS at different times of treatment, ranging from 15 min to 24 h (Fig. 1). Peroxidation of membrane lipids was analyzed as level of thiobarbituric acid reactive substances (TBARS) after treating HSC with 20 ng/ml of TNF- α for 24 h. As shown in Table 1, the content in TBARS was not altered by treatment with TNF- α , being similar in TNF- α -treated HSC to that of untreated control cells. Unlike ROS generation and lipid peroxidation, intracellular

GSH levels of HSC were altered by treatment with TNF- α . HSC incubated with 20 ng/ml TNF- α for 24 h showed a 30% decrease on GSH levels as compared to control HSC (Table 1).

3.2 Role of GSH on the antifibrogenic effect of TNF- α on HSC

Since we had found TNF- α to produce a depletion of GSH levels on HSC, we studied the possible role played by this alteration on the antifibrogenic effect of TNF- α . HSC were treated with two concentrations of GSH (1.0 and 2.0 mM) prior to incubation with TNF- α , and after 24 h intracellular GSH levels were measured as before. Table 2 shows that both pretreatments prevented the depletion of GSH levels caused by TNF- α , with values similar or slightly higher to those found in untreated cells. Once we had established the conditions to restore GSH intracellular levels depleted by TNF- α , we analyzed the effect of blocking GSH depletion on procollagen a1(I) mRNA levels. HSC were incubated with 20 ng/ml of TNF- α for 24 h, conditions that provoke a decrease on colla1 mRNA levels of 40% [14]. Northern blot analysis of colla1 mRNA levels revealed that pretreatment of HSC with either concentration of GSH was able to abolish the inhibitory effect of TNF- α , since cells pretreated with GSH and incubated with TNF- α presented colla1 mRNA levels similar to those of untreated cells (Fig. 2).

To determine if the effect of GSH on the inhibitory action of TNF- α was due to its antioxidant action, other compounds with different antioxidant effects were evaluated: tempol, deferoxamine and trolox. Although not being ROS-specific, these compounds have been described as scavengers for O₂⁻, OH[·] or derivatives of lipid peroxidation, respectively. HSC were pretreated for 30 min before treatment with TNF- α with the antioxidants and 24 h later colla1 mRNA levels were determined by Northern blot. As shown in Fig. 3, none of the antioxidants used prevented the inhibition of colla1 mRNA levels caused by TNF- α -on HSC.

3.3. Regulation of NF κ B by GSH on TNF- α -treated HSC

Activation of NF κ B by TNF- α was then evaluated. EMSA analysis showed that treatment of HSC with TNF- α for 2h caused an increased binding of nuclear proteins to the consensus probe for NF κ B. By supershift assays the DNA-bound proteins were identified as p50 and p65 homo- or heterodimers (Fig. 4 a).

To establish whether GSH depletion by TNF- α was related to the activation of NF κ B, HSC were pretreated with GSH as above, and EMSA analysis for NF κ B binding carried out after treating the cells for 2 h with TNF- α . As shown in Fig. 4 b, pretreatment with 2.0 mM GSH prevented NF κ B activation induced by TNF- α on HSC. None of the other antioxidants tested, deferoxamine, tempol or trolox, abolished NF κ B activation in a similar way when added prior to TNF- α .

Discussion

TNF- α , a cytokine with apoptotic and proinflammatory effects in different cell types, is one of the few agents capable of inducing a down-regulation on procollagen $\alpha 1(I)$ (coll1a1) production by HSC without affecting cell survival. We had previously characterized some molecular mechanisms of TNF- α action on HSC, like inhibition of p38 MAPK phosphorylation and activation of members of nuclear factor C/EBP family [22,14]. In the present work we sought to investigate the role played by oxidative stress, which presents profibrogenic effects on HSC but is induced by TNF- α in other cell types. We found that in HSC, TNF- α did not alter lipid peroxidation or ROS production, suggesting that oxidative stress does not mediate TNF- α -effects on coll1a1 expression. The only parameter related to oxidative stress that changed in response to TNF- α -was the intracellular content of glutathione (reduced form, GSH), an effect that has been described for other cell types in response to different agents [23]. In previous studies we demonstrated that GSH depletion in HSC treated with 3,4-methylenedioxymethamphetamine (MDMA, "Ecstasy") mediated the induction of coll1a1 mRNA levels, but this effect correlated to increased ROS production and was abolished by pretreatment with antioxidants different from GSH, like deferoxamine [24]. In the present work, we found that a decrease in GSH levels in the absence of increased ROS production mediates the down-regulation of coll1a1 mRNA levels by TNF- α , and that pretreatment with GSH but not with other antioxidants prevents the effect of this cytokine. These results suggest that ROS production is a key event for coll1a1 induction in response to oxidative stress in HSC, and that in our system GSH exerts its action through a mechanism which is independent of its antioxidant potential.

Some of the effects of GSH depletion in other cell types have been shown to be due to the activation of neutral sphingomyelinase, an enzyme involved in ceramide production and ERK activation in response to TNF- α [25,26]. In our experimental system, however, this does not seem to be the mechanism through which GSH depletion mediates the effect of TNF- α on collagen production. As we have already demonstrated, ERK activation is not responsible for the antifibrogenic action of TNF- α , since inhibition of ERK phosphorylation did not affect the down-regulation of coll1a1 mRNA levels induced by TNF- α [22]. The involvement of p38, a key regulator of collagen production in HSC, was also ruled out since GSH pretreatment did not alter the effect of TNF- α on its phosphorylation levels (data not shown).

There is experimental evidence for the role played by NF κ B activation in the down-regulation of collagen type I production in HSC. Transient transfection of HSC with NF κ B p50 and p65 expression plasmids caused a strong inhibitory effect on transcription of the coll1a1 gene promoter [27], and a new NF κ B binding site in the promoter of procollagen $\alpha 2(I)$ involved in the down-regulation of the gene has been described [28]. In agreement with previous reports [16], we found that TNF- α induced NF κ B activation in HSC, although in our hands TNF- α increased both p50 homodimer and p50/p65 heterodimer binding to NF κ B consensus sequence, while Novitskiy et al. described an increase of p65 but not of p50 in response to the cytokine. This discrepancy could be due to different experimental approaches, since those authors analyzed nuclear protein levels and not binding activity of the components of NF κ B. NF κ B activation correlated to the inhibitory effect of TNF- α on coll1a1 mRNA levels. Interestingly, this correlation was also observed using GSH and antioxidants: NF κ B activation was abrogated by GSH but not by deferoxamine, tempol or trolox. These results also indicate that NF κ B activation and the regulation of NF κ B by GSH are

not related to the generation of oxidative stress. Other authors have described a modulation of NF κ B by GSH in agreement with our findings [29].

In summary, GSH depletion contributes to the inhibitory effect of TNF- α on *coll1a1* mRNA levels in HSC through mechanisms that are independent of oxidative-stress generation and prevent NF κ B activation.

Acknowledgments

This work was supported by Fondo de Investigaciones Sanitarias (FIS) 00/0143 and PI030391 grants.

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Figures

Figure 1

Fig. 1. Time course analysis of reactive oxygen species (ROS) levels on HSC treated with TNF- α HSC were exposed for 0.5, 2, 4, 8 and 24 h to 20 ng/ml TNF- α and ROS levels determined by fluorimetry, using CMH₂DCFDA as a probe. Treatment with menadione (100 μ M, 2 h) was used as a positive control. Each bar represents the means \pm SD of fluorescence fold change compared to controls of at least quadruplicate experiments (* p < 0.05, vs control).

Figure 2

Fig. 2. Northern blot analysis of procollagen $\alpha 1(I)$ (*col1a1*) mRNA levels of HSC pretreated with GSH and treated with TNF- α . HSC were incubated for 30 min with 1.0 or 2.0 mM GSH prior to TNF- α treatment. Northern blot analysis was performed with 10 μ g of total RNA extracted 24 h after treating the cells with TNF- α (20 ng/ml). Each bar represents the means \pm SD of at least quadruplicate experiments. Values were corrected for loading differences after hybridization with a cDNA probe for 18 s ribosomal RNA. (* $p < 0.05$; a, vs control; b, vs TNF- α -treated cells).

Figure 3

Fig. 3. Northern blot analysis of procollagen $\alpha 1(I)$ (*col1a1*) mRNA levels of HSC pretreated with either deferoxamine, tempol or trolox, and treated with $TNF-\alpha$. HSC were incubated for 30 min with 0.1 mM deferoxamine, 2.0 mM tempol or 1.0 mM trolox prior to $TNF-\alpha$ treatment. Northern blot analysis was performed with 10 μ g of total RNA extracted 24 h after treating the cells with $TNF-\alpha$ (20 ng/ml). Each bar represents the means \pm SD of at least quadruplicate experiments. Values were corrected for loading differences after hybridization with a cDNA probe for 18s ribosomal RNA (* $p < 0.05$; a, vs control; b, vs $TNF-\alpha$ -treated cells).

Figure 4

Fig. 4. EMSA analysis of NFκB activation induced by TNF-α. HSC were treated for 2 h with 20 ng/ml TNF-α and nuclear extracts obtained as indicated in Section 2. Reaction mixtures contained 10 μg of protein and, when indicated, 1.0 μg of antibody against p50 or p65. (a) Antibody competition assay for NFκB-bound proteins. (b) Effect of GSH and antioxidants on NFκB activation. HSC were pretreated with either 2.0 mM GSH, 0.1 mM deferoxamine, 2.0 mM tempol or 1.0 mM Trolox before adding TNF-α to the cell cultures.

Table 1Effect of TNF- α on intracellular GSH levels and total lipid peroxidation

	GSH (nmol/106 cells)	MDA (nmol/106 cells)
Control	7.55 \pm 0.51	0.19 \pm 0.09
TNF- α	5.76 \pm 0.45**	0.17 \pm 0.19 (n.s)

HSC were treated for 24 h with TNF- α (20 ng/ml) and glutathione (reduced form, GSH) levels and malondialdehyde (MDA) content determined as described in Section 2. Values are the means \pm SD of at least quadruplicate experiments (**p < 0.01, vs control).

Table 2

Effect of exogenous GSH on GSH intracellular levels depleted by TNF- α

	Treatments					
	Without GSH		GSH 1mM		GSH 2mM	
	Control	Tnf- α	Control	Tnf- α	Control	Tnf- α
GSH intracellular levels (nmol/106 CEH)	7.39 \pm 0.23	3.76 \pm 0.43**	12.56 \pm 1.25**	9.83 \pm 0.6**	18.24 \pm 0.25**	12.55 \pm 1.6**

HSC were pretreated for 30 min with 1.0 or 2.0 mM GSH and treated with TNF- α (20 ng/ml). After 24 h intracellular GSH levels were measured as described in Section 2. Values are the means \pm SD of at least quadruplicate experiments (**p < 0.01, vs the corresponding control).